

What do stakeholders perceive as the benefits and drawbacks associated with transparency in the implementation of blockchain technology within the agri-food supply chain?

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Introduction

Blockchain, a decentralized and distributed digital ledger technology, has the potential to revolutionize record-keeping across various sectors by enabling secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant data storage and processing without the need for a central authority (Ruoti et al., 2019). In recent years, a substantial body of research has emerged on integrating blockchain technology (BCT) across various sectors (Frizzo-Barker et al., 2020). Particular attention has been paid to areas with increased traceability requirements, such as the Food Supply Chain (FSC). The FSC faces significant challenges in terms of transparency, efficiency, and security, which blockchain technology promises to address (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021; Zhao et al., 2019). This promise has led to numerous pilot projects across the globe: Walmart (Hyperledger, 2019), Auchan (CNS Media, 2018), Nestlé (Nestlé, 2019), and World Wildlife Fund (WWF) (Cook et al., 2018) implemented blockchain-based traceability systems.

Despite the seeming success of these pilot projects, widespread adoption of blockchain in the agri-food industry has not yet materialized. This lack of widespread adoption suggests that while blockchain has the potential to resolve many of the issues plaguing the agri-food supply chain, there must be significant factors preventing its broader implementation. One of such factors could be conflicting views on blockchain's transparency (Zhang et al. 2021; Zhao et al., 2019). Transparency, a characteristic feature of blockchain, is a multifaceted concept encompassing an organization's willingness to share information, the clarity with which that information is conveyed, and the reliability and truthfulness of the disclosed content (Schnackenberg & Tomlinson, 2014). While it is often cited as an

advantage in ensuring food safety, quality, and ethical sourcing, it may also present unprecedented challenges in the management of the agri-food supply chain, acting as a double-edged sword (Kamilaris et al., 2019). Attitudes towards transparency vary among FSC participants, with some preferring more extensive privacy and others benefiting from increased data availability (Thompson & Rust, 2023).

To fully understand the potential impact of blockchain transparency on the agri-FSC, it is crucial to investigate stakeholders' perceptions of its benefits and barriers. However, little research involves the supply chain actors (Thompson & Rust, 2023). This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the central question: *"What do stakeholders perceive as the benefits and drawbacks associated with transparency in the implementation of blockchain technology within the agri-FSC?"* By examining stakeholders' views, this research seeks to provide nuanced insights into the privacy-transparency dichotomy and assess their diverse needs. Focusing specifically on transparency can help to understand how stakeholders' perceptions of the benefits and drawbacks associated with blockchain transparency play a role in determining the BTC adoption within the agri-FSC.

To answer the posed research question, this paper is organized into five sections:

1. Research Context of Blockchain in the FSC: Gives a literature review of the current landscape of BCT in the food supply chain and its perceived benefits.

2. Methodology: Details the steps of the thematic analysis and data collection methods.

3. Results: Presents the findings from the thematic analysis.

4. Discussion: Interprets the results, with the focus on the perceived benefits and trade-offs of blockchain and their influence on blockchain adoption, and relates them to existing literature.

5. Conclusion: Summarizes the key findings and discusses implications for future research and practical applications in the FSC.

Research Context

The discourse on BCT within the FSC gained momentum with Walmart's proof-of-concept initiative of a blockchain-based food traceability system in 2016. As documented by Hyperledger (2019), Walmart successfully used Hyperledger Fabric blockchain platform for its Chinese pork and US mangoes supply chains. Also in 2016 started the integration of TE-FOOD blockchain into the various supply chains of the French retailer Auchan (CNS Media, 2018). The successful outcomes of the pilot studies led to more FSC companies attempting to leverage blockchain. For instance, Nestlé partnered with OpenSC to develop a blockchain-based system for tracking milk from farms in New Zealand to factories in the Middle East (Nestlé, 2019). Another notable example is the WWF in Australia, Fiji, and New Zealand that collaborated with ConsenSys, TraSeable, and Sea Quest Fiji Ltd. to use blockchain technology for tracking tuna with the goal of sustainable and ethical fishing practices (Cook et al., 2018). Notably, these projects used different blockchain platforms but had one common goal to provide transparent information about the origin of food products.

Despite the several successful practical demonstrations, subsequent explorations into blockchain's application in the FSC have largely remained

conceptual. Limited empirical research can potentially be explained by the lack of blockchain experts to support the systems (Frizzo-Barker et al., 2020) and the infancy of technological development (Vu et al., 2023). The novelty of the technology makes empirical research more difficult, yet more pressing.

Multiple scholars, including Frizzo-Barker et al. (2020), Pandey et al. (2022), Thompson & Rust (2023), and Vu et al. (2023), have underscored the need for data-driven research to effectively guide blockchain's implementation within the FSC. Additionally, the literature consistently highlights the critical role of stakeholder involvement, suggesting that the perception of blockchain's value by the FSC participants is a decisive factor for its adoption (Thompson & Rust, 2023). Multi-stakeholder engagement could be particularly advantageous and help account for the challenges faced by newer or smaller actors (Pandey et al., 2022).

Further literature review evidenced that one of the key broadly recognized advantages of BCT is transparency (Ellahi et al., 2023; Frizzo-Barker et al., 2020). Yet, not all stakeholders value it to the same extent, nor do all blockchain configurations offer the same level of transparency, as noted by Behnke & Janssen (2020). Several papers illustrate that entities such as wholesalers might seek greater control over information to preserve competitive advantages (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Thompson & Rust, 2023; Zhang et al., 2021). Hence, they are more reluctant to adopt a technology that can undermine it. From the interviews with supply chain actors at different levels, Thompson & Rust (2023) further point out that even if some stakeholders favor a higher level of decentralization and information sharing, they may still be hesitant to implement blockchain due to the fear of "jeopardizing relationships with

these wholesalers upon which their business models rely." Such concerns could potentially be addressed through the use of private blockchains (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021; Vu et al., 2023). However, the caveat around permissioned (private) systems lies in the potential cost of diluting blockchain's inherent transparency, which is its main value proposition (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021; De Ruyter De Wildt, 2020). The question then arises: *To what extent is transparency favorable among the different stakeholders within the FSC?* On one hand, a higher consumer demand for transparency could push large actors towards more openness (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021; Thompson & Rust, 2023). On the other hand, big players are likely to be the main drivers of initial blockchain adoption (Thompson & Rust, 2023), and full transparency may be disincentivizing for them.

This privacy-transparency dichotomy of BCT is entering the broader discourse of transparency brought by technology. Schnackenberg and Tomlinson were among the first to analyze the significance and meaning of transparency in multi-stakeholder organizations in 2014. Flyverbom (2016) further delved into the interplay between visibility and transparency, and the power dynamics emerging from it. The author highlighted that transparency is not a binary state, but a dynamic concept that requires ongoing negotiation and recalibration. Furthermore, Flyverbom argued that increased data availability may disguise itself as transparency while creating new forms of opacity and obfuscation, such as when powerful actors selectively disclose or withhold information, creating a carefully curated narrative.

Building on the foundation, this research investigates the stakeholders' perceptions of the negative and positive aspects of blockchain transparency. A

thematic analysis of primary stakeholder input is particularly pertinent considering the current research focus on conceptual frameworks with minimal human involvement.

Methodology

The data for this research was collected through participation in the trans-disciplinary multi-stakeholder research process conducted by the Athena Institute on behalf of the TRUSTyFOOD project. TRUSTyFOOD is designed following backcasting (Vergragt & Quist, 2011) and co-creation methods.

During the data collection phase, a series of five stakeholder workshops was held. The setup of the workshops was a variation of a focus-group research design, each revolving around one of the key FSC stakeholder groups: farmers, agro-food sector companies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), blockchain companies, and policymakers. Table 1 gives a brief description of each group.

However, for a more meaningful analysis of the large amount of data from the workshops, this paper focuses on the first two out of five stakeholder groups, farmers and agro-food companies. The groups were chosen due to their foundational role in the supply chain; their perceptions should be investigated first to derive implications for higher level stakeholders. Furthermore, these groups represent a wide range of operational scales, from family farms and startups to multinational corporations. This allows for a more nuanced understanding of the perceptions of blockchain transparency in different contexts.

Table 1

Stakeholder Groups Outline

Stakeholders	Description
Farmers	The primary producers within the FSC; can operate at different scales.
Agro-food companies	A wide array of entities linking farmers and consumers and involved in food processing, packaging, and distribution.
NGOs	Social organizations outside of the FSC that can influence the policies implemented within the FSC.
Blockchain companies	Companies offering blockchain solutions to agro-food companies and aiding in its technical implementation.
Policymakers	Government representatives that craft and implement regulations affecting all participants in the FSC.

A four-phase thematic analysis of the chosen workshops was conducted following the methodology adapted from a publication by Vaismoradi et al. (2016). The phases and their constituent stages are outlined in table 2.

Table 2
Thematic Analysis Process

Phase	Stages
Initialization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transcribing workshop recordings and familiarizing with the data. 2. Reducing the data through coding (identification of the key stakeholder perceptions of blockchain transparency) 3. Annotating the data with potential interpretations.
Construction	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thematically classifying the identified codes into perceived benefits and drawbacks of blockchain transparency. 2. Comparing the identified groups of codes to draw plausible themes in the data. 3. Labeling the themes with representative sentences derived from conversation topics.

Phase	Stages
	4. Defining the derived themes and reporting on the analysis process and how they relate to each other.
Rectification	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Distancing from the data for a period of time and discussing the analysis with other researchers participating in the project. 2. Relating the identified themes to the existing body of research. 3. Stabilizing the themes by elaborating on subthemes and including the examples of codes on which the themes are based.
Finalization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a coherent narrative through connecting the themes by outlining stakeholders' general views and highlighting opposing interests in transparency.

The chosen conceptual framework guiding the coding process is primarily inductive. This approach allows for a granular examination of the stakeholder's perceptions of the benefits and drawbacks of blockchain transparency. The more nuanced coding is unlike that in existing research, which often considers the trade-off between transparency and privacy as a singular code with little attention to the different types of blockchains. Hence, this study aims to capture a broader spectrum of considerations and stakeholders' expectations.

Results

Figure 1

Perceived Benefits and Barriers: Themes

Perceived benefits of transparency

1. Consumer interaction

1.1. *"Consumer demand of transparency"*

It was consistently mentioned that the pressure from the consumers to be able to see the information about the products they are buying could be a key driving factor to adopt BCT. The stakeholders also expected that consumers would like to know the information not only about the production of food, but also its potential environmental impact. One of the participants noted: *"In the case of traceability, the consumer demand for more transparency could encourage manufacturers to use this technology."* This highlights the role of consumer expectations in driving the whole supply chain towards using blockchain to achieve greater transparency.

1.2. *"Market appeal"*

The majority of stakeholders noted that transparency could be most beneficial for marketing. For instance, one of the participants mentioned how their business openness was a part of their promotion strategy, and thus they would like to *"make the products more story-tellable"* with blockchain-enabled transparency. Such ability to showcase the production pipeline was mentioned as a way of *"creating a competitive advantage through transparency in quality."*

1.3. *"Consumer trust"*

One of the key re-emerging conversation topics among stakeholders was the blockchain's *"confidence-building"* ability to enhance consumer trust in the product. For example, here is a representative quote from one of the stakeholders: *"Blockchain could provide accountability of data, which is fundamental for trust between producers and consumers."* This enhanced trust could be superficial, as one of the stakeholders stated that simply mentioning blockchain in the name of the

project could lead people to trust the information more. However, it could also be more concrete, as others mentioned *"data on blockchain as a proof of impact."*

1.4. *More effective consumer communication*

The stakeholders expressed how using blockchain and being transparent about the processes could allow for working towards a common goal: *"better communication with the customer, we are really stronger together."* They also mentioned that information transparency about various products could allow consumers to *"easily compare and understand the different flow for the creation of the different product."*

2. Legal and financial benefits

2.1. *"Guarantee for shared added value"*

Stakeholders cited a variety of the legal and financial advantages of blockchain's transparency. One farmer mentioned that blockchain could provide a *"guarantee for shared added value along the whole supply chain,"* ensuring an equitable distribution of value at each production stage. One of them highlighted that incorporating economic information into the blockchain could solve issues of uneven value distribution by aggregating data related to each step, thereby contributing to the final product's value.

2.2. *"Fair price to farmers and for the consumers"*

On the financial side, they emphasized that blockchain ensures a *"fair price to farmers and for consumers,"* noting that if this technology can achieve fair pricing for all parties involved, it would be a *"total success."*

2.3. *Legal efficiency and cost-effectiveness*

Additionally, blockchain's potential to replace traditional certifications with more cost-effective transparency measures was underscored, with one stakeholder stating: *"transparency is cheaper than certifications,"* making it a valuable tool for legal efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

3. *Food fraud solution*

The potential to combat food fraud with blockchain's transparency was one of the key themes. It was described as *"good solution for food fraud"* and *"very important for safety food."* Additionally, stakeholders emphasized the need for transparency to cultivate a *"virtuous food system,"* where the integrity of products is maintained, thus fostering not only trust, but also safety throughout the supply chain.

4. *Traceability and information access*

Stakeholders underscored the importance of BCT for enhancing traceability and information access within the supply chain. It was emphasized that a *"transparent blockchain"* serves as an effective tracking technology, ensuring *"transparency and traceability"*, where *"each and every farmer will have access to everything."* However, they noted that a *"prior agreement on data to be searched,"* would be necessary. Such an agreement would ensure that all relevant information is efficiently and consistently tracked and shared.

Perceived barriers of transparency

1. Diverse needs of different stakeholders

- 1.1. *Loss of "profit from lack of information" and "competitive edge"*

The primary barrier to blockchain transparency was centered around the perceived loss of competitive advantage. One major concern was that many players currently *"profit from lack of information"* and have *"no interest in sharing information because they profit from misinformation and missing information."* The particular unwillingness to share the pricing information was underscored. The phrase *"lose control"* encapsulated the anxiety among certain actors who are hesitant to move towards transparency in fear of undermining their established market position.

- 1.2. *Difficulties achieving consensus in a multi-stakeholder environment*

Another concern was about the complex multi-stakeholder environment of the supply chain and the consequent difficulty achieving consensus: *"the more stakeholders you have, the harder it is to work towards a common goal."* Stakeholders stated that it is difficult to select information that benefits all parties, as what helps marketing might not necessarily assist dairy farmers, complicating the alignment of interests.

- 1.3. *"Not every participant wants transparency"*

Some stakeholders questioned: *"But who really wants transparency?"* and pointed out that *"some business models wouldn't support full transparency."* Additionally, specific examples were given, such as Senegalese farmers who might be more interested in practical benefits like opening a bank account rather than the transparency that blockchain systems provide.

2. Accountability of information that is put on blockchain

2.1. *Selectiveness of information*

Stakeholders acknowledged the selectiveness of information when required to fill out tracking details: *"we could put the information that we want."* Thus, it would be a question of who is responsible for logging the data onto the blockchain, leading to potential *"unbalanced storytelling."* Concerns were also raised about the authenticity of reported data, as one stakeholder mentioned the difficulty in ensuring that *"what you see on paper is what actually happens inside the companies."* This raises fears that compliance may become merely a facade, with companies superficially meeting requirements without genuine transparency. However, participants noted that the issue could be mitigated by introducing random third-party audits.

2.2. *Doubts of the transparency guarantees*

Participants also expressed doubts about the transparency guarantees of blockchain systems. One participant questioned: *"Is the transparency being guaranteed?"* while another highlighted the *"guarantee transparency [of] data input"* as a barrier. These concerns underscore the skepticism towards the ability of the system to assure genuine transparency across the supply chain.

3. Initial implementation challenges

3.1. *Lack of standards*

Lack of standards has been discussed in detail. One participant noted that integrating IoT to enhance the transparency of the blockchain without clear

standards could lead to unreliable data, while another mentioned the confusion around what needs to be tested and required from them.

3.2. *Alternative technologies*

It was pointed out that blockchain is not the only option, as *"there are a lot of other technologies that validate transparency"* and ensure data immutability. One participant mentioned that *"we're not there yet"* with blockchain and there are technologies with more advanced transparency features *"where you can have selective disclosures and protect all the sensitive information."*

3.3. *"Resistance to change"*

Stakeholders noted *"resistance to change"* that could arise due to fear, inertia, and satisfaction with current status. They suggested that strong regulation may be required to have the supply chain actors transition to become more transparent.

4. *"Data privacy concerns"*

Participants highlighted issues such as *"data exposure"* and noted that, in complex supply chains with multiple players, *"there is the privacy and confidentiality issue."* One participant who had experience with the IBM pilot blockchain project¹ observed that *"competitors didn't want to disclose their own data in this consortium,"* reflecting a general reluctance of the actors to share sensitive information.

5. *"Mistrust in the technology"*

¹ IBM. (n.d.). *IBM Food Trust - Blockchain for a transparent supply chain*. Retrieved May 21, 2024, from <https://www.ibm.com/products/supply-chain-intelligence-suite/food-trust>

Stakeholders mentioned a significant *"mistrust in the technology,"* which leads to the situation where *"people are just scared to give away precious information."* This lack of trust extends to business models and is compounded by a *"lack of knowledge and trust from producers."*

6. *"Lack of added value"*

Participants noted *"no awareness of the benefits"* of blockchain and stated that *"people are unwilling to share information until they see the benefit that will come out of it."* Misunderstanding of the technology was mentioned as one of the factors contributing to the problem: *"when we say blockchain, people think of crypto or Bitcoin and that the added value is not evident."*

7. *Difficulties with consumer communication*

Participants expressed their perceived difficulty in consumer communication with: *"I'm not sure I can communicate my point and the very meaning of the information to the customer."* The issue was closely related to the perceived added value of the technology by the consumers. One of the stakeholders mentioned the risk of overwhelming consumers with too much information, leading them to feel *"drowning in it."*

Discussion

The results of this study revealed diverse stakeholder perspectives on the role of BCT in enhancing transparency within agri-FSC. Key themes that emerged include the influence of consumer demand, the potential for blockchain to foster trust, the use of blockchain for compelling storytelling, legal and financial implications, issues

around food fraud and data authenticity, and the challenges of technological readiness and multi-stakeholder coordination. This discussion explores these themes, synthesizes them with existing literature, and provides insights into their implications for blockchain adoption in the FSC.

One of the primary driving forces for adopting blockchain transparency identified by stakeholders is consumer demand. Agri-food companies emphasized the growing pressure from consumers who seek detailed information about production processes and environmental impacts. This shift towards sustainability and ethical sourcing aligns with established consumer trends (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021). Some farmers also recognized blockchain's ability to enhance product narratives, making transparency a potent marketing tool. The highlighted benefit of transparency-based storytelling for engaging the consumer and enhancing competitive differentiation was also brought up in literature by Frizzo-Barker et al. (2020). Yet, a counter-narrative emerged from others who expressed skepticism about consumers' genuine interest in blockchain transparency. This disparity unveils a critical challenge: aligning the perceived consumer demand with actual market behaviors. Enhancing consumer education on blockchain's benefits could bridge this perceptual gap, fostering a more unified approach toward transparency.

Intertwined with consumer demand is the theme of trust. Blockchain technology was recognized for its potential to enhance consumer trust through greater data availability, accountability, and general perceptions of blockchain as a trustworthy technology. Stakeholders highlighted how blockchain could build confidence in product information, a sentiment echoed in the literature that

underscores the importance of transparency in building trust (Schnackenberg & Tomlinson, 2014). However, multiple stakeholders noted that trust could be superficial due to a lack of accountability of the data entered into the blockchain. This further indicates a divide between consumers and producers: while transparency can potentially increase consumer trust, there is significant mistrust among producers regarding the technology, which may hinder its implementation. To mitigate this issue, the study participants called for random human-led third-party audits to ensure the authenticity of data inputs.

The perceived lack of accountability is tangent to the concerns about selectiveness of information disclosure. Participants noted that data logged onto the blockchain might only represent what certain parties choose to disclose, which could ultimately unfairly skew the narrative. This issue has also been highlighted in literature on transparency by Flyverbom (2016). Stakeholders emphasized the necessity for standardized protocols and regulations that ensure comprehensive and accurate information sharing from all parties.

Notwithstanding the expressed concerns about the selectiveness and lack of accountability of information input, stakeholders envisioned the potential for blockchain to combat food fraud through transparency. They also discussed how blockchain's traceability could help quickly locate and isolate contaminated or expired food, thereby enhancing food safety. This advantage has indeed been noted as one of the main drivers for blockchain implementation (Ellahi et al., 2023; Kshetri, 2019). However, the findings from the workshops are more nuanced: there was consensus among stakeholders that for such a system to be accountable, there

need to be understandable standards, enforceable regulations, and independent third-party audits.

Other drivers of transparency were the legal and financial implications. Stakeholders, particularly farmers, saw a great potential in blockchain to ensure fair value distribution along the supply chain and reduce costs associated with traditional certifications. These benefits underscore blockchain's capacity to address economic disparities within the FSC by providing transparent mechanisms for tracking economic information. However, the transparency of economic information was not universally welcomed. While it is seen as a tool for more equitable pricing benefiting farmers and consumers, agri-food companies agreed that disclosing too much information, particularly economic details such as pricing, is a significant competitive disadvantage. Zhang et al. (2021) reached a similar conclusion in a modeling study. The results point that the unwillingness of companies to share sensitive pricing information could halt blockchain technology adoption at an early stage. So, the benefits of transparency may be perceived as unevenly distributed.

The opposing interests in how much economic information is shared highlights the compounding coordination challenges in a multi-stakeholder environment. The FSC's inherent diversity, with its varying priorities and needs, makes consensus-building difficult. However, this complexity issue – highlighted by numerous participants – was contrasted with the view that blockchain could be used as a tool for fostering collaboration and mutual support. These findings add to the literature on multi-stakeholder engagement, which emphasizes the need for nuanced

approaches to balance interests and achieve successful collaboration (Pandey et al., 2022; Flyverbom, 2016).

While many aspects of transparency elicited contrasting perceptions among stakeholders, certain issues were universally seen as obstructive, particularly those related to technological readiness and resistance to change. The absence of industry standards, both on the use of blockchain and the type of information required for sharing, and the presence of alternative technologies were frequently cited as significant hurdles. Additionally, concerns over data privacy and a reluctance to share sensitive information further complicate blockchain adoption efforts. Yet, these challenges are not unprecedented and have been discussed in previous literature, for instance by Zhao et al. (2019). The persistence of the same barriers over the years highlights the critical need for clear guidelines and educational initiatives to enhance understanding and acceptance of blockchain within the FSC.

While the explicit stakeholders' comments paint a clear picture that agrees with existing literature, it is important to note what has not been mentioned during the workshops. There is a notable discourse gap in the lack of distinction between public and private blockchains. As noted on literature, such distinction is important as the chosen type of blockchain could significantly influence the level of transparency and privacy achieved with the technology (Bischoff & Seuring, 2021; Vu et al., 2023). While one participant noted that there is technology that allows for selective information disclosure, they said that blockchain was not yet there. This signifies that they were not aware of the existence of private blockchains. However, little distinction between blockchain types in literature should also be acknowledged.

Conclusion

This study explored stakeholders' perceptions of the key benefits and drawbacks associated with transparency in the implementation of blockchain technology within the agri-food supply chain. The findings revealed diverse perspectives on the role of transparency, with stakeholders expressing both optimism and concerns regarding its impact on the sector.

Oposing views were held on multiple issues. Stakeholders recognized the potential of blockchain-enabled transparency to enhance consumer trust, combat food fraud, and ensure fair value distribution. Transparency driven by consumer demand is seen as a critical driver for blockchain adoption, yet its success hinges on addressing significant concerns about data accountability and selective information disclosure. The potential of transparency to combat food fraud and ensure food safety is promising, but its efficacy depends on rigorous standards and third-party audits to maintain data integrity. The legal and financial benefits of transparency, such as ensuring fair value distribution and reducing certification costs, are evident. However, the reluctance to share sensitive pricing information poses a considerable barrier that needs strategic solutions balancing transparency with competitive interests.

To fully realize the potential of transparency in blockchain implementation, the agri-food supply chain must overcome challenges related to technological readiness and resistance to change. Establishing clear industry standards for transparency and promoting educational initiatives will be crucial in enhancing understanding and acceptance of blockchain-enabled transparency. Additionally, fostering collaboration

among diverse stakeholders through pilot projects can demonstrate the practical benefits of transparency and mitigate speculative perceptions.

Most of the perceived benefits and drawbacks of transparency identified in this study are rather general and have been noted in existing literature. This observation could indicate that stakeholders indeed share similar opinions, or it might suggest that participants, lacking hands-on experience, were speculating based on what they have heard and read. Education and test bed projects could help producers formulate more specific comments and opinions on transparency. However, the study's limitation that the workshop setup was not directly investigating transparency but the larger topic of BCT perceptions, should be acknowledged. Nevertheless, education and test bed projects have a great potential to help stakeholders formulate more specific opinions on transparency based on practical insights. The missing education on the subject was noticeable based on the lack of distinction between private and public blockchains. Given the stakeholders' concerns surrounding the interplay of transparency and privacy, and the notable differences between blockchain types, the distinction could provide a more nuanced understanding of feasibility of blockchain implementation in the agri-FSC.

Future development of this research would benefit from involving a wider range of stakeholders, including blockchain companies, NGOs, and policymakers. While more empirical studies could provide great insight into the actual impact of transparency, multiple issues need to be addressed to ensure that such pilot and empirical research on transparency progresses smoothly and does not halt at an

early stage. Developing a set of standardized protocols is of uppermost importance. Additionally, based on stakeholders' feedback, investigating different audit mechanisms that could ensure the authenticity and reliability of data in transparent blockchain systems would be beneficial. By addressing these aspects, the agri-food supply chain can harness the potential of blockchain-enabled transparency to enhance trust and efficiency.

Ethics

The study will be conducted as part of the TRUSTyFOOD project and hence falls under its ethics management plan. All participants sign an informed consent form, their data is anonymized and stored on protected servers.

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